

Symposia “in honor of . . .” generally tend toward the reflective as colleagues and protégés outline the guest of honor’s legacy. It’s indicative of Francis X. Blouin’s thirty-two years of pioneering leadership as director of the University of Michigan’s (U-M) Bentley Historical Library that the Visual Culture and Archives Symposium on April 4–5, 2013, marking his retirement was a forward-thinking event. Thirty-three speakers across twelve panels demonstrated Blouin’s influence in their own visual culture work. The presentations also illustrated his impact on how archivists and researchers encounter visual culture in the archives.

A commonality among the papers was how archival practice neither begins nor ends in the archive. Instead, archival practice travels across formats, time, geographies, ideologies, and institutions. This archival mobility means that our practice toward the visual has to adapt continually. In his remarks, Blouin offered a hat-tip to his colleagues at the Bentley who pushed him to recognize the importance of photography in the archives. It was in this spirit that Joan Schwartz (Queen’s University) offered a series of provocations on whether we value and preserve digital photography with the same methods applied to print

**VISUAL
CULTURE
COUP**

**Bentley Symposium
Honors Retiring Director**
Francis X. Blouin

**Kimberly Springer,
MSI 2014, School of Information,
University of Michigan**

photography. Early in the proceedings, she alluded to a theme across several papers: What can we learn about preserving born-digital materials from our experiences with analog? Notably digital photography was accepted reluctantly as archive-worthy, with

both Schwartz and Krzysztof Pijarski (Film School, Łódź, Poland) questioning both what we choose to archive and how this is done.

Archivists, researchers, and practitioners took the audience on a wide-ranging journey into the following: digital reunification for Filipinos’ collective memory; the intimacies of mourning and gendered implications of archiving Poland’s photographers for the Archaeology of Photography Foundation; finding evidence of Robert Rauschenberg’s artistic practice in the *New York Times* and *Life* magazine digital archives; U-M’s late 1800s–early 1900s zoology expeditions; and the heart of digital representations of Big Data in the archives. Paul Conway, U-M professor in the School of Information, nicely encapsulated the symposium’s implicit theme in his presentation on users’ decision-making around photographic archives. He observed—applicable to his presentation, but extrapolated to other panels—that the most interesting and innovative archival work “lives at the intersection of discovering, storytelling, and landscape.”

One presentation I found emblematic of the high level of scholarly and affective investment in the meaning of archives was

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Rukantabula began visiting TBC to speak with its chief librarian, Bruno Nanguka, to forge a partnership. Nanguka knew firsthand the challenge they faced but was open to the idea. He'd slowly been digitizing the tapes himself, but for him to copy all of the 100,000 hours of material in the archive was estimated to take 15 years—if he worked nonstop.

Rukantabula and Corey, who later returned to Tanzania to see the project through, partnered with other key groups, including Tanzania's Ministry of Information and Culture, the Copyright Society of Tanzania, and the National Arts Council. To establish THP as a trusted organization, they registered it as an NGO with the Tanzanian government.

Using Kickstarter

Corey and Rukantabula put in countless hours of work, but they wanted others to feel as connected to the project as they did. They envisioned a collaborative project that encouraged engagement as much as preservation. To raise funds, Corey turned to Kickstarter, an online fundraising platform, and spread the word about the project through updates on Kickstarter, Facebook, Twitter, and emails and phone calls to family and friends.

They launched the project on Kickstarter in December 2011 with a \$13,000 goal. Donations came in from around the globe.

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choreographer and dancer Peter Sparling's "Body Poetics in the Time of Digital Babel: The Screendancer as Poet/Archivist." Timing his recitation with his own archival footage of dance (now housed in the Bentley), as well as new digitally captured material, Sparling offered the audience a masterful critique of his own subjectivity as an object within the archives and as a user coming from outside the archive to use his own materials. In the context of the other presentations, Sparling's approach to inside/outside worked for his exploration of embodiment but also reached to other presentations, such as Kilian Klug (Plural, Berlin) and his discussion of representing

One backer had visited Tanzania on his honeymoon. Another had served in the Peace Corps there. Others simply had a passion for music. They also were embraced by the Tanzanian community, who craved reminders of home or a way to reconnect with their past. By February 2012, THP had 235 backers and had raised \$17,040.

For Corey, the money was icing on the cake. The real reward, she says, was finding the supporters and forming personal connections with them.

"Some people pointed out to me that with all the time we spent running the Kickstarter campaign, we could have made the same amount [of money] if we just worked full-time jobs," Corey says. "But I think doing that would be missing the point. Kickstarter is about much more than just the money—it's about involving people in a project you care about and want to share with the world."

Digitizing the Tapes

The funds are being used to provide TBC with equipment needed to digitize the tapes, cover a Radio Tanzania digitization workshop to train locals on the digitization process, and pay royalty fees to Tanzanian musicians and the government. They also plan to release a "Best of Radio Tanzania" CD with liner notes and photographs.

THP has teamed up with UNESCO to complete digitization of the reel-to-reel tapes, with TBC taking the lead in managing the project. Digitization is expected to begin this year and will take between three and

archival data via development of an Interactive Research Table, which provides an intuitive access to digital archives and cross-media storytelling. Boundaries were necessarily blurred in pushing the audience to think beyond disciplinary lines.

The symposium, which was organized by the Bentley's Acting Associate Director Nancy Bartlett, wrapped up with Blouin's enthusiastic assessment that intellectual synergy was achieved; boundaries were pushed and connections made to archives and other communities. He noted that his retirement from the Bentley this August will be in the nick of time: Born-digital presents new challenges in appraisal. "In the spirit of where I am, good luck! Tell me how it turns out!" Blouin quipped.

Holdings at the Tanzania Broadcasting Corporation archives. *Courtesy of Jonathan Kalan.*

four years. As the music is digitized, THP will make it accessible online to bring the music to audiences who already love it and those who have yet to discover it.

THP has grown from a lofty idea that Corey thought up to a full-fledged operation, complete with a "business guy," "social media guru," and other team members. The heart of the operation, though, remains giving Tanzanians—and the world—a way to learn about the country's cultural identity.

"The initial vision Benson and I shared was that the Tanzania Heritage Project would be about much more than preservation for preservation's sake," Corey says. "Rather, [it was about] preservation as a means to an end—to ownership and pride in Tanzanian culture; economic development; community access to the archives; and an invaluable historical resource for scholars, educators, and researchers." ■

Based on the packed house of colleagues, students, archives users, and other guests who crowded into the Rackham Amphitheater for a concluding tribute, it's a safe bet that Blouin won't get away from the archives community that easily nor any time soon. He'll continue to influence archival practice in innovative ways beginning next fall as professor in U-M's Department of History and School of Information.

A publication of the symposium presentations, to be coproduced by the Bentley and SAA, is in the offing. In the meantime, video for the symposium and the tribute to Blouin are at <http://bentley.umich.edu/general/symposiumvideo.php>. If you'd like to catch up on the panels through tweets, U-M's SAA chapter (@mich_archives) covered most, if not all, of the panels with #bhlvisual. ■